

Flick of a switch: regulatory mechanisms allowing *Listeria monocytogenes* to transition from a saprophyte to a killer

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Abstract

In contrast to obligate intracellular pathogens that can remain in relatively stable host-associated environments, the soil-living bacterial pathogen *Listeria monocytogenes* has to sense and respond to physical and chemical cues in a variety of quite different niches. In particular, the bacterium has to survive the dramatic transition from its saprophytic existence to life within the host where nutritional stress, increased temperature, acidity, osmotic stress and the host defences present a new and challenging landscape. This review focuses on the σ^B and PrfA regulatory systems used by *L. monocytogenes* to sense the changing environment and implement survival mechanisms that help to overcome the disparate conditions within the host, but also to switch from a harmless saprophyte to an impressively effective pathogen.

INTRODUCTION

Listeria monocytogenes is a Gram-positive human bacterial pathogen that is able to cause infections in mainly immunocompromised hosts. The infections, commonly known as listeriosis, can be very severe with a mortality rate of between 20 and 30%. Typically, infection by *L. monocytogenes* is caused by ingestion of contaminated food, which enters the intestine via the oral route (Fig. 1) [1]. In order to survive the harsh environment in the stomach and intestine, the bacterium has to deploy a number of protective mechanisms. In particular, the pathogen uses glutamate decarboxylation and arginine deimination to assist with intracellular pH homeostasis in response to acidic stress. It deploys a bile salt hydrolase and multidrug efflux systems to protect against bile stress. While in the face of hyperosmotic stress, it uses compatible solute transport systems for efficient osmoregulation. Many of these systems are actively upregulated upon entry into the host and are under the control of the alternative sigma factor sigma B (σ^B), the master transcriptional regulator of the general stress response in this pathogen (reviewed in [2–5]).

Once inside the gut, the bacterium is able to cross the intestinal barrier by attaching to epithelial cells using bacterial adhesins with specific host receptors, such as the InlA:E-cadherin interaction. After uptake, the bacterium can lyse

the vacuole through the action of a haemolysin, LLO, and two phospholipases, PlcA and PlcB. Once inside the cytosol, *L. monocytogenes* takes up phosphorylated sugars such as glucose 6-phosphate through a transporter, Hpt, to be able to replicate. Through the action of ActA, the Arp2/3 complex is recruited, mediating actin polymerization and protrusion of the bacterium to the adjacent cell. Once there, the double membrane vacuole is lysed, again by the action of LLO, PlcA and PlcB [1]. After host cell adhesion and uptake, the transcriptional activator PrfA controls several subsequent steps, although other regulatory pathways also contribute [6, 7].

In this review, we focus on the two most prominent regulatory systems in *L. monocytogenes*, σ^B and PrfA. We discuss evidence for the interplay between these regulatory systems and describe how they can act synergistically to stimulate expression of commonly regulated genes. The complex overlap between these systems suggests that there is a fine balance between surviving harsh environments in the food chain and gastrointestinal tract and successfully colonizing the host, and understanding this balance may ultimately be a key step in controlling this pathogen. Because there is large variation among different *L. monocytogenes* strains, care should be taken when interpreting the data of each individual experiment if using another strain background.

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Abbreviations: FA, fatty acid; GABA, gamma aminobutyric acid; GI, gastrointestinal; QS, quorum sensing; UTR, untranslated region.

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Fig. 1. Schematic overview of *Listeria monocytogenes* colonization of the intestine by pathways being controlled by σ^B and/or PrfA. The human microbiota is depicted on top, lying over the microvilli-containing epithelial cells. Below are shown the events, which are controlled by regulators (σ^B or PrfA) that in turn regulate expression of important factors. A time-line of events during *L. monocytogenes* passage of the intestinal barrier is shown at the bottom.

Reprogramming transcription for survival: coping with stress

In response to changing conditions bacteria rapidly modulate their transcription to better equip themselves for the new prevailing environment. There are multiple regulatory networks that feed into this process and collectively these serve to fine tune the expression of genes and regulons in order to favour survival and growth in the new conditions. At the top of the regulatory hierarchy are the sigma factors that control the genes that can be accessed by the transcriptional machinery, by determining the promoter recognition capacity of RNA polymerase. Most strains of *L. monocytogenes* have five sigma factors, including the housekeeping sigma factor σ^A , as well as σ^C , σ^H , σ^I and the stress-inducible sigma factor, sigma B (σ^B). Analysis of the regulons under the control of the four alternative sigma factors reveals that σ^B controls the largest regulon, approximately 300 genes [8, 9]. As such it contributes to many facets of the biology of this pathogen including stress tolerance and homeostasis, biofilm regulation, cell-wall turnover, survival within the mammalian gastrointestinal (GI) tract and even the response to visible light [2, 10, 11].

Functions under σ^B control

In recent years a plethora of transcriptomic and proteomic studies have been conducted to help define the full extent of the σ^B regulon [8, 9, 12–22]. While the functions of many genes in the regulon remain to be established, it is clear that many of the genes under σ^B regulation contribute to protective, homeostatic and repair functions.

An early finding was that σ^B contributes to acid resistance, a phenotype that is essential in allowing the pathogen to transit

the acidic mammalian stomach and colonize the GI tract [23, 24]. Although σ^B appears not be essential for the adaptive acid tolerance response or for stationary-phase-induced acid tolerance it does contribute to the regulation of the glutamate decarboxylase acid tolerance system [19, 24–26]. The decarboxylation of glutamate to gamma aminobutyrate (GABA) contributes to cytoplasmic pH homeostasis and is essential for glutamate-dependent acid tolerance [27, 28]. σ^B is also required for expression of *lmo0913*, encoding a succinyl semialdehyde dehydrogenase, which is involved in the GABA shunt pathway that allows GABA to be converted to succinate [20, 29].

L. monocytogenes is very osmotolerant, being capable of growth in media containing up to 2 M NaCl [30]. This makes it a particular challenge for food producers that rely on reduced water activity to preserve ready-to-eat foods. Its capacity for efficient osmoregulation using compatible solutes such as glycine betaine and carnitine are crucial for this osmotolerance. The OpuC ABC transporter is required for carnitine transport, while the BetL and Gbu transporters are required for glycine betaine uptake under conditions of osmotic stress [31–34]. The expression of OpuC is dependent on σ^B and indeed carnitine transport is abolished in a *sigB* mutant [32]. The expression of Gbu is partially dependent on σ^B , with one of the two promoters preceding *gbuA* being σ^B -dependent [35].

A role for σ^B in resistance to the bacteriocins, nisin and lactacin and to antibiotics such as penicillin G and ampicillin has been reported [36, 37]. Interestingly *dapE*, a gene encoding succinyl-diaminopimelate desuccinylase, which is required for peptidoglycan biosynthesis, has been reported to be σ^B -dependent [20]. This could account for an alteration in

Gram staining described for the *sigB* mutant and could also contribute altered sensitivity to cell-wall-acting antimicrobials [21].

Several lines of evidence suggest that *L. monocytogenes* σ^B is crucial for colonization of the host GI tract [2–4]. First, σ^B is required for the expression of bile salt hydrolase and *sigB* mutants are extremely sensitive to bile [38, 39]. The BilE system, reported to be a bile efflux system, is also known to be under σ^B control [32, 40]. *L. monocytogenes* is able to colonize the murine gall bladder [41], where bile is largely non-toxic because of the elevated pH [42]. However, when bile is released into the duodenum the toxicity increases because of the low local pH, and in this environment the SigB-dependent bile resistance mechanisms play a crucial role in survival [42]. Second, the σ^B -dependent OpuC carnitine transport system has been shown to be required for efficient colonization of the murine intestine [43]. Third, in a guinea pig infection model σ^B is required for infection following oral inoculation of the animals but is not required when *L. monocytogenes* is introduced intravenously. Finally, a transcriptomic study of *L. monocytogenes* in the mouse reveals that the σ^B regulon is highly upregulated in the intestine but not in the blood [16]. Remarkably the invasion genes *inlA* and *inlB*, which are co-transcribed, and *inlD* are also under σ^B control, although the virulence regulator PrfA also plays a role in their expression [44, 45]. It is interesting to speculate that cell invasion could be a stress mitigation strategy insofar as it allows the pathogen to escape the comparatively harsh conditions found

in the lumen of the intestine to the more benign conditions found within the cytoplasm of host cells.

Because σ^B contributes to both survival and pathogenesis within the host, as well as to survival outside the host, a better understanding of the mechanisms that activate this sigma factor could be a crucial step for the development of new antimicrobials to control this pathogen. However, the mechanisms that control the deployment of this transcriptional regulator are complex and currently not well understood. The complexity of the control mechanisms probably reflects the fact that choosing to invest cellular resources in protection instead of growth has important repercussions for fitness.

Stressosome composition and function

L. monocytogenes uses a sophisticated mechanism to control the activation of σ^B that relies on a ~1.8 MDa supramolecular complex known as the stressosome, which is believed to act as a sensory hub. This complex, which has thus far been mostly studied in *Bacillus subtilis*, is thought to integrate and transduce environmental stress signals that modulate σ^B activity to produce a transcriptional response appropriate to the changing environmental conditions [46, 47]. The operon encoding the key components of the stressosome (*rsbR*, *rsbS* and *rsbT*) and the downstream signalling pathway (*rsbU*, *rsbV*, *rsbW*, *sigB* and *rsbX*) are organized in a similar way and the gene products are highly conserved between *B. subtilis* and *L. monocytogenes* (Fig. 2a) [48]. In both

Fig. 2. a. Graphical representation of the *L. monocytogenes* *sigB* polycistronic operon, depicting the genes coding for stressosome components and the downstream signal transduction and the promoter regions controlled by the *L. monocytogenes* housekeeping sigma factor A (σ^A) and the alternative sigma factor B (σ^B). The suggested function of the gene products is shown on top. b Schematic overview of the stressosome complex. The 1.8 MDa stressosome complex is built-up by three proteins, RsbR, RsbS and RsbT at a stoichiometry of 40:20:20, respectively. The N-terminal, globin-like structures of RsbR (pink) protrude from the stressosome core, consisting of the C-terminal STAS domain of RsbR and STAS domain of RsbS (both in blue) as well as the RsbT (green). See text for further details. The cartoon is adapted from [49]

species, the stressosome is composed of RsbS, RsbR and RsbT (Fig. 2b) with a probable stoichiometry of 20:40:20, respectively [47, 49]. While *B. subtilis* possesses several RsbRA paralogues scattered throughout its genome (RsbRB, RsbRC, RsbRD and YtvA), *L. monocytogenes* RsbR (Lmo0899) paralogues can also be found (Lmo0161, Lmo0799, Lmo1642 and Lmo1842) [50, 51]. In *L. monocytogenes*, the stressosome can be anchored to the inner surface of the cell membrane through a small membrane-spanning protein, Prli42. Immunoprecipitation experiments targeting Prli42 identified the RsbR paralogues Lmo0161, Lmo0799 and Lmo1642 (but not Lmo1842) among the components associated with the stressosome. Prli42 has therefore been suggested to play a role in stress sensing and signal transduction initiation, although the mechanism for this is unclear at present [52].

The stressosome's core structure is formed by the conserved STAS-containing (Sulphate Transporter and Anti-Sigma factor antagonist) C-terminal domains of RsbS and RsbR that can self-assemble, as the STAS domains acts as a scaffold for the complex assembly [52, 53]. Approximately 20 stressosomes are present within each *B. subtilis* cell [54]. At the stressosome surface, turrets formed by the RsbR N-terminal domains fold into globin-like structures, which are thought to work as stress sensors. Unlike the haem groups identified in *Vibrio vulnificus*, *Chromobacterium violaceum*, *Ruegeria* species and fatty acids in *Bacillus anthracis*, no cofactor has thus far been identified associated within the RsbR globin-like structures in *B. subtilis* or *L. monocytogenes* [54–56]. The single exception to this is *B. subtilis* YtvA and *L. monocytogenes* Lmo0799, which fold into a Light-Oxygen-Voltage (LOV) domain that forms a covalent bond with a flavin mononucleotide (FMN) in response to blue light [50, 57]. Although homodimers of *B. subtilis* RsbR paralogues have been shown to associate *in vitro* [58, 59], it remains unknown if heterodimeric associations between RsbR and its paralogues can also occur. Yet it is worth noting that immunoprecipitation and two-hybrid experiments suggest that YtvA may bind with RsbRA and RsbRD; moreover, in the absence of RsbRA, YtvA is not assembled into the stressosome, thereby abrogating the blue-light-sensing capacity of *B. subtilis* [60–62]. These results suggest that either RsbRA acts as scaffold for YtvA in the stressosome or that RsbRA:YtvA dimers may form in the stressosome.

After assembly, RsbR and RsbS are able to sequester RsbT and form the core stressosome complex. The kinase activity of RsbT can lead to the phosphorylation of conserved serine and threonine residues in the STAS domains of RsbR and RsbS in response to stress signals, although the phosphorylation kinetics of the stressosome are not entirely understood [63]. Phosphorylation of the STAS domains triggers a release of RsbT from the stressosome, which in turn initiates the downstream partner switching module leading to σ^B activation. The exact sequence of events leading to RsbT release remain unclear, although a study of the blue light sensor YtvA in *B. subtilis* suggests that once the stress is sensed, a conformational change propagates from the RsbR N-terminal to the C-terminal STAS domain through the α -helix connecting

the two domains [64]. This results in a rearrangement of the architecture of the stressosome core, which reduces its affinity for RsbT, thereby leading to its release from the stressosome [65–67]. Studies in both *B. subtilis* and *Vibrio brasiliensis* suggest that phosphorylation by the RsbT kinase of conserved threonine and serine residues within the RsbR and RsbS STAS domains is essential for signal transduction through the stressosome, as mutating these residues compromises the ability to activate σ^B in response to stress [63, 68–70]. The threonine residues at positions 171 and 201 in RsbRA of *B. subtilis* are conserved in all RsbR paralogues with the exception of YtvA [63, 69]. *L. monocytogenes* RsbR also possess these conserved threonines in positions 175 and 209, but these residues are not conserved in the other RsbR paralogues (Lmo0161, Lmo0799, Lmo1842, Lmo1642), although negatively charged residues present at these positions could potentially mimic phosphothreonines [57]. If this is the case then two possibilities exist that remain to be investigated experimentally. Either the STAS domains of the RsbR paralogues adopt a conformation that leads to RsbT release by a mechanism that is independent of phosphorylation or these proteins are phosphorylated at alternative positions which have yet to be identified. Nonetheless, in *B. subtilis*, stressosome activation is dependent on RsbT kinase activity, as mutations that lead to the inactivation of the kinase result in strains that are no longer able to activate σ^B in response to stress [65]. If the residues are not phosphorylated at the serine/threonine residues of RsbR/RsbS, the RsbT is no longer able to dissociate from the stressosome and activate the signal transduction during the onset of stress [71, 72].

Once the signal transduction has been initiated and σ^B reaches its peak of activity, the stressosome is deactivated by the action of the phosphatase RsbX that dephosphorylates RsbR and RsbS, thereby facilitating the re-sequestration of RsbT into the non-phosphorylated stressosome core and resetting the stressosome to a sensing-ready state [66, 73].

Mechanisms of sensory perception by the stressosome

L. monocytogenes is capable of sensing a variety of stresses via the stressosome, but the molecular mechanisms by which the RsbR paralogue(s) contribute to this in response to different stress signals remain largely unknown. As there is only weak conservation of the RsbR N-terminal domains, with only 17–20 % sequence identity between the RsbR paralogues [58], it has been hypothesized that each paralogue may detect different stress signals. Multiple knockout deletions of the *B. subtilis* RsbR paralogues revealed significant redundancy in the system as different mutants that each express a single RsbR paralogue can all respond to ethanol stress, albeit with different σ^B activation kinetics [63, 74]. Furthermore, a previous study has shown that a series of strains carrying single knockout mutations in each of the *L. monocytogenes* RsbR paralogues do not exhibit altered stress-related phenotypes [75]. Together these findings suggest that there is redundancy in the stressosome stress-sensing mechanism of both *B. subtilis* and *L. monocytogenes*.

The only RsbR paralogue in *L. monocytogenes* that is conserved across species is the phototropin Lmo0799, which shares 54 % homology with the blue-light sensor from *B. subtilis* YtvA [50, 76–78]. These proteins have LOV domains that associate with FMN molecules and once exposed to blue-light the FMN oxidizes and forms a covalent adduct with a conserved cysteine (C56 in *L. monocytogenes* and C62 in *B. subtilis*), triggering a structural rearrangement that propagates to the Ja-helix, generating changes in the dimer interface of these phototropins [50, 64, 79, 80]. Missense mutations that alter these conserved cysteine residues abrogate the light-sensing mechanism as FMN is no longer able to bind to the cysteine and trigger the downstream activation of σ^B [77, 81, 82]. Unlike YtvA, Lmo0799 appears to be less stable, due to the lack of positively charged residues in the LOV domain. This promotes FMN dissociation, especially at higher temperatures [83], suggesting that blue-light sensing may be affected by temperature in *L. monocytogenes*.

As discussed, activation of the stressosome by stress relies on the phosphorylation of threonine residues located in the RsbR and RsbS C-terminal STAS domains. The Thr171 of *B. subtilis* RsbRA is phosphorylated by RsbT even in the absence of stress [67]. Substitution of the conserved threonine residue (T171) with alanine seems to diminish the activation of σ^B and reduces the phosphorylation of RsbS Ser59, suggesting that Thr171 phosphorylation is required for stressosome activation [63, 67, 68]. Interestingly, substituting Thr205 with alanine in RsbRA of *B. subtilis* results in a constitutively active stressosome which, unlike the native stressosome, remains highly active following high-stress treatments, such as 54 °C and 10 % ethanol [63]. This result suggests that Thr205 phosphorylation plays a role in attenuating signal transduction through the stressosome under severe stress conditions [73]. Meanwhile, substitutions of RsbRA Thr171 and Thr205 with negatively charged aspartic acid residues, which mimic a phosphorylated residue, seemly do not affect the stressosome activation by stress [63]. Despite the advances made, the full details of how phosphorylation contributes to the modulation of the activity of the stressosome are still not well understood.

Events downstream of the stressosome in the σ^B regulatory pathway

The stress signals sensed and transduced by the stressosome result in the release of RsbT from the stressosome core, and this is thought to be responsible for initiation of the downstream regulatory events that result in σ^B activation [84]. RsbT can associate with the phosphatase protein RsbU and this interaction activates its phosphatase activity [71]. The substrate for this reaction is phosphorylated RsbV. When RsbV is dephosphorylated it can interact with RsbW, the anti-sigma factor that binds to σ^B , preventing it from associating with RNA polymerase under non-stress conditions [71]. This preferential interaction of RsbW with unphosphorylated RsbV shifts the equilibrium such that σ^B becomes available to interact with RNA polymerase and to initiate transcription of the σ^B regulon. In *B. subtilis* the phosphorylation state of RsbV can also be influenced by the activity of RsbP, a phosphatase

whose activity is triggered by energy stress (depleted ATP pools) in a manner that depends on its interaction with RsbQ and is independent of the stressosome [85]. This system is absent in *L. monocytogenes* and it appears that all stress signals are detected and propagated by the stressosome [86]. Indeed, the RsbR protein from *L. monocytogenes* can replace the RsbRA protein in *B. subtilis* and allows both energy and chemical stress signals to be transduced [46]. Thus, activation of σ^B appears to depend primarily on the phosphorylation state of RsbV. However, evidence for an alternative route for σ^B activation in *L. monocytogenes* comes from the observation that an *rsbV* deletion mutant, which should not be able to sequester RsbW from σ^B , shows signs of σ^B activity at low temperatures, suggesting that in this case some mechanism exists downstream from RsbV to trigger the activation of σ^B [87, 88]. While the mechanism underlying this effect has not been identified, it is possible that alternative routes for σ^B activation are present, allowing a short circuiting of the stressosome sensory hub under some conditions.

PrfA – a master regulator of virulence

After its passage into the epithelial cell layer of the intestine, intracellular growth and survival of *L. monocytogenes* depends on a multitude of virulence factors, which have to be expressed at the right time and place. Expression of the large majority of these virulence factors is controlled by the main virulence activator PrfA, a 27 kDa protein belonging to the Crp/Fnr family of transcriptional regulators [89–92]. PrfA acts by binding as a dimer to a palindromic consensus binding site, known as the PrfA-box, lying upstream (~40 bp) of the transcriptional start sites of genes that are positively controlled by PrfA. Absence of PrfA severely attenuates *L. monocytogenes* virulence, in both vertebrate and invertebrate as well as cell culture infection models [90, 93, 94]. Due to its importance for pathogenesis, expression and activity of PrfA are controlled at several levels (transcriptional, post-transcriptional and post-translational) to ensure that virulence genes are transcribed only when necessary within the host (Fig. 3). Indeed, inappropriate expression of virulence genes outside the host is associated with a significant fitness cost [95, 96].

Transcriptional regulation of *prfA* expression

The first stage of *prfA* regulation occurs at the transcriptional level where three different promoter regions ensure the proper expression of *prfA* depending on the various conditions *L. monocytogenes* encounters. Two of these promoter regions, P1 and P2, are located just upstream of the *prfA* coding sequence (Fig. 3a) [97]. Transcription from either of these promoters gives rise to monocistronic *prfA* transcripts. Transcription from the P1 promoter is mediated by the housekeeping σ^A sigma factor. Interestingly, the P2 promoter region consists of two overlapping promoters, one that is recognized by the σ^A sigma factor and another that is recognized by σ^B [98–100]. A putative PrfA binding box is located in the P2 promoter region and serves to establish a negative autoregulatory loop. Transcription of *prfA* from P1 and P2 is negatively regulated

Fig. 3. (a) Regulation of PrfA expression and activation. The *prfA* transcript is expressed from three different promoters, the P1- (regulated by σ^A), the P2- (regulated by σ^A and σ^B) and the *plcA*-promoter (creating a *plcA-prfA* bicistronic messenger). The *plcA* promoter is positively regulated by active PrfA, creating a positive feedback loop of PrfA expression. (b) The *prfA* messenger is post-transcriptionally regulated, through a thermosensor which inhibits ribosome binding at low temperatures, but also by two RNAs, SreA and SreB, which bind and block PrfA expression. (c) Post-translational modification of PrfA. Reduced glutathione (GSH) binds PrfA and sterically changes the position of the helix-turn-helix motif to promote DNA binding to the PrfA binding site (green box). Activity of PrfA is also known to be affected by other factors but by which mechanisms they affect PrfA activity are not yet known.

by PrfA itself but this negative feedback system appears not to influence virulence in mouse models of infection, but rather that it might have a role in suppressing virulence outside the host [90, 97]. The direct effect by PrfA on the P2 promoter is, however, unclear because *in vitro* transcription of the *prfA* gene from neither the σ^A nor the σ^B P2 promoters is affected by the presence of PrfA [99]. Under certain forms of stress, transcription from the P2 promoter is enhanced, demonstrating a role of σ^B in *prfA* expression (Tiensuu and Johansson, unpublished observations) [98, 101].

The third promoter regulating *prfA* transcription, P3, is located upstream of the *plcA* gene and is PrfA-regulated [91, 102]. From this promoter *prfA* is transcribed bicistronically together with *plcA* and is dependent on PrfA activation at temperatures higher than 30 °C [103]. A positive feedback loop is generated as PrfA will induce its own synthesis, which will cause the amount of *prfA* to increase to levels that are required for full virulence capacity [90, 97, 102].

Another mechanism of transcriptional regulation of *prfA* has been shown to involve the global metabolic regulator CodY, which is able to sense the concentration of branched chain amino acids (BCAAs). Under situations when BCAA concentrations are low, for example inside mammalian host cells, virulence gene expression is induced [104]. In the absence of bound isoleucine, CodY binds within the *prfA* gene approximately 15 nt downstream of the start codon and

thereby activates *prfA* transcription [105]. This unusual and not yet fully understood mechanism serves as a way to sense the metabolic environment and adjust the virulence gene expression accordingly. Activity of CodY is also controlled by different secondary messengers such as ppGpp, c-di-AMP and c-di-GMP [106, 107]. The levels of PrfA are thus indirectly controlled by external stress cues via CodY activity.

Post-transcriptional control of PrfA expression

Expression of PrfA is increased at body temperature (~37 °C), mainly due to an RNA thermosensor located at the 5'-untranslated region (5'-UTR) lying in front of the *prfA* encoding mRNA expressed by the P1 promoter (Fig. 3b) [108]. At low temperatures, the *prfA* 5'-UTR forms a stable hairpin that prevents primary binding of the ribosome to the Shine-Dalgarno (SD) region and thus translation initiation. At permissive temperatures, a region in the hairpin close to the SD region is opened up, allowing binding of the ribosome and PrfA expression [108, 109]. Because translation of the transcripts generated from the P2 promoter region is not temperature-dependent (only one stem of the RNA thermosensor) this allows production of PrfA even when *L. monocytogenes* is grown at stress conditions at low temperatures.

Expression of PrfA is also controlled by two prematurely terminated S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) responsive riboswitches, SreA and SreB [110]. Riboswitches are RNA

elements that are able to directly bind specific metabolites to control expression of coding mRNAs lying 3', on the same transcript [111]. In Gram-positive bacteria, the binding of a metabolite (such as SAM) to a riboswitch generally causes transcriptional termination, preventing further transcription of the downstream mRNA. As a consequence, relatively small (~100–250 nt) RNA fragments are produced. Two of these, SreA and SreB, are able to directly bind to the 5'-side of the *prfA* thermosensor hairpin and inhibit PrfA expression through a still-unknown mechanism. Thus, SreA and SreB function as typical *trans*-acting small RNAs (sRNAs – see below) [110]. Interestingly, both SreA and SreB are unable to bind the *prfA* thermosensor at low temperatures, when the latter adopts a 'closed' conformation. The *prfA* 5'-UTR can thus act as a sensor, integrating temperature (through its thermosensing properties) with the metabolic state of the bacterium (through expression of SreA and SreB), in order to fine-tune PrfA expression and virulence factor expression.

Post-translational regulation of PrfA

PrfA belongs to the cyclic AMP receptor protein (Crp) family of transcriptional activators [112]. This family of proteins typically bind a co-factor (e.g. cAMP binding to CRP) that causes an allosteric change which in turn induces DNA binding activity. Structural similarities to CRP and studies of mutant strains where PrfA is constitutively and fully activated (*prfA*^{*}) suggested a signal or a cofactor to activate PrfA [113, 114]. After decades of research, a genetic screen succeeded in identifying this allosteric activator as glutathione (Fig. 3c) [115]. Glutathione is a tripeptide that in its reduced form (GSH) can function as an antioxidant protecting cells from oxidative damage. GSH binds directly to a tunnel site in PrfA, causing a conformational change that increases binding of PrfA to the PrfA-box and promotes transcription of PrfA-regulated genes [116, 117]. Unlike most Gram-positive bacteria *L. monocytogenes* is able to synthesize GSH by expressing glutathione synthase, encoded by *gshF*, but can also transport exogenous GSH into the bacterial cell [118]. Upon mammalian cell infection *gshF* becomes 10-fold upregulated. Furthermore, Δ *gshF* mutant strains are less virulent in mice [115]. Growing *L. monocytogenes* *in vitro* in a nutrient-limited reducing medium gives rise to PrfA activation that is dependent on intracellular GSH [119]. Because the host cell cytosol is a reducing environment where the concentration of GSH is high, sensing of the redox status might be the cue to drive appropriate virulence factor expression.

PrfA activation is also correlated with sugar metabolism, which might serve as an additional way for *L. monocytogenes* to sense the environment. When living as a saprophyte, *Listeria* utilizes sugars such as cellobiose and glucose that are taken up by the phosphoenolpyruvate phosphotransferase system (PTS), and this is known to inhibit virulence factor expression [120–122]. However, growth in non-PTS sugars such as glycerol and phosphorylated sugars such as glucose 1-phosphate, which are major carbon sources in the host cell, does not lead to repression of virulence factor expression [123]. In the host cell, *L. monocytogenes* expresses the

PrfA-regulated gene *uhpT* that encodes a transporter of phosphorylated sugars which, when being imported, are metabolized in the bacterial pentose phosphate pathway [124]. The nature of different carbon sources might therefore regulate virulence factor expression.

Being a food-borne bacterium, *L. monocytogenes* is exposed to a variety of fatty acids (FAs) found in food and in the host GI tract. Certain free FAs have been found to harbour antibacterial properties and to affect virulence [125]. For instance, medium- and long-chain FAs in *Salmonella* and *Vibrio* species have been found to inhibit virulence factor expression [126, 127]. Interestingly, in *Vibrio cholera* long-chain FAs bind directly to the virulence regulator ToxT and thereby inhibit virulence factor expression possibly by disturbing ToxT dimerization and DNA binding [128–130]. FAs have also been suggested to have a role in *L. monocytogenes* virulence. Metabolic supplementation with various FA precursors to wild type strains shows reduced expression of the virulence factors *hly* and *inlA* [131]. Furthermore, addition of medium- and long-chain free FAs reduces virulence factor expression in wild type strains which, interestingly, is also observed in a constitutively active *prfA* mutant (*prfA*^{*}) [132]. This suggests that the repressive effect of the FAs occurs after PrfA activation and that FAs could possibly interact directly with PrfA or act as signalling molecules to downregulate virulence expression.

Although a better understanding of the mechanisms underpinning the impact of redox conditions, sugar and fatty acid availability on virulence are still needed, it seems clear that *L. monocytogenes* is able to sense and integrate many environmental signals to produce precisely the right level of PrfA activity for each niche encountered.

Evolutionary maintenance of PrfA

While being absolutely required for bacterial virulence in the host cell, several studies also suggest a function for PrfA outside the host. Constitutive activation of PrfA enhances virulence but reduces the fitness of bacteria in both broth culture and soil [95, 96]. Although maintaining virulence genes should be a burden for the bacterium outside the host, long-term stationary-phase growth of *L. monocytogenes* does not interfere with its virulence capabilities [133]. There is therefore no selective disadvantage for the bacterium in retaining the virulence genes under non-infective conditions and such loss-of-virulence function mutations have only been observed at a low frequency in naturally occurring isolates of *L. monocytogenes* [134].

Interestingly, in culture experiments where environmental stresses such as heat and salt stress are applied, fluorescent reporter fusions show a stochastic activation of both σ^B and PrfA, with the proportion of cells with active PrfA being higher than cells with active σ^B [135]. This could indicate that, under certain conditions, it is beneficial for the bacterium to have many cells in the population with active PrfA while only a subpopulation express active σ^B , for example as a bet-hedging strategy to cope with drastic environmental

changes. Further studies will be needed to better understand this unexpected and interesting stress response.

In the environment, *L. monocytogenes* often forms biofilms to colonize various surfaces. PrfA has been shown to promote biofilm formation both at 37 and at 23 °C [78, 136]. Furthermore, the PrfA-regulated virulence factor ActA, which is responsible for the spread of *L. monocytogenes* between host cells, has also been found to function extracellularly to promote *L. monocytogenes* aggregation, biofilm formation and persistence in the gut lumen [137]. Perhaps it is these auxiliary roles that provide the necessary selective pressure to maintain PrfA and the virulence factors it regulates when the bacterium is outside the host cells.

Regulation by RNA

The *prfA* thermosensor is not the only 5'-UTR controlling expression of its downstream gene. The 5'-UTRs of *hly*, *actA* and *inlA* are all important to control expression of LLO, ActA and InlA, respectively [138–140]. In contrast to the *prfA* thermosensor, the 5'-UTRs of *hly*, *actA* and *inlA* all appear to stimulate protein production, although the mechanisms remain unclear. Interestingly, expression of the *inlA-inlB* bicistronic messenger is initiated at several promoters, one being σ^B -dependent and another PrfA-dependent. Thus, it seems that *L. monocytogenes* engages both of these regulatory pathways to ensure InlA and InlB expression when necessary. Also, the sizes of the 5'-UTRs being produced by PrfA-activated and σ^B -dependent promoters are different, potentially allowing the formation of alternative 5'-UTR RNA structures, an additional level of regulation.

Small *trans*-acting regulatory RNAs (sRNAs) are regulatory molecules of different sizes (~100–500 nt) controlling gene expression in response to different environmental cues. They do so by different mechanisms, generally involving direct base-pairing between the sRNA and a region close to the SD of the target mRNA, often destabilizing the latter by the action of RNases. In *L. monocytogenes*, more than 100 sRNAs have been identified but the role for the majority of these in gene regulation remains unknown [16]. Expression of at least two of the sRNAs is controlled by σ^B , namely SbrA and Rli33-1, the latter being part of the LhrC family of sRNAs [141, 142].

It has been shown that expression of several sRNAs is induced when *L. monocytogenes* enters a host cell [143]. One intracellularly induced sRNA is Rli27, which has been shown to bind the 5'-UTR of *lmo0514*, encoding a cell-wall-binding LPxTG protein [144]. The 5'-UTR of *lmo0514* can form a repressive RNA-hairpin preventing translation initiation, but the binding of Rli27 to the 5'-UTR disrupts the hairpin and translation can initiate, allowing intracellular expression of Lmo0514.

Members of the large family of LhrC sRNA variants control expression of several target mRNAs, both in an overlapping but also in a unique manner and are induced when the bacterium is exposed to blood [16, 141, 145–147]. Among the genes being controlled are three mRNAs encoding virulence factors:

LapB – an adhesin; TcsA – a T-cell-stimulating antigen; and OppA – a component of an oligopeptide permease system. CU-rich loops in the LhrC sRNAs bind to regions overlapping the SD of the target RNA, thereby blocking translation initiation and thus protein production. Interestingly, expression of LapB is also controlled by PrfA, allowing dual regulation of the adhesin [148]. At least one two-component system (TCS; discussed further below), LisRK, has been shown to regulate expression of several of the LhrC family members [146]. The LisRK–LhrC regulatory pathway allows the bacterium to quickly adopt the expression of several genes in response to different environmental cues.

Two-component systems

Among the strategies used by bacteria to detect and transmit environmental stimuli to generate an appropriate transcriptional response, the so-called TCSs are probably the best studied. In bacteria, TCSs are widespread and have been reported to respond to changes in a number of different environmental conditions. Typically, a TCS is composed of a sensor (a histidine kinase, HK) that monitors external signals and a response regulator (RR) that controls gene expression or other physiological activities of the bacteria. They accomplish signal transduction through phosphorylation of the RR by the HK. HKs are typically homodimeric transmembrane proteins containing a histidine phosphotransfer domain and an ATP binding domain. RRs are usually multi-domain proteins with a receiver domain and at least one effector, often involved in DNA binding (Fig. 4) [149, 150].

Once a change in the extracellular environment is detected the HK is autophosphorylated, by the transfer of a phosphoryl group from ATP to a specific histidine residue (His). The cognate RR then catalyses the transfer of the phosphoryl group to an aspartate residue (Asp) on its receiver domain. This triggers a conformational change that activates the RR's effector domain, resulting in the appropriate transcriptional response to the environmental input received, usually by stimulating (or repressing) expression of target genes. Thus, the TCSs ensure optimal growth by aligning gene expression to the prevailing conditions. Signal transduction is shut off by either spontaneous hydrolysis of the phosphorylated RR (RR ~P) or by dephosphorylation of the RR ~P, either by the phosphatase activity of the cognate HK or by another specific phosphatase [149].

In *L. monocytogenes* TCSs play an important role in adaptation to the many stress factors encountered in nature, during food processing or inside the host. The *L. monocytogenes* genome harbours 15 HKs and 16 RRs, including DegU, which is an orphan RR [151]. Several of the *Listeria* TCSs have been also implicated in virulence [152–155].

One of the best-studied quorum-sensing (QS)/TCS mechanisms is the Agr system of *Staphylococcus aureus*. It is composed of a four-gene operon encoding four proteins: AgrB, which is responsible for the export and the proteolytic processing of the QS peptide AgrD into an auto-inducing peptide (AIP); and AgrC (histidine kinase) and AgrA

Fig. 4. A summary of regulatory events underlying stress regulation and virulence factor expression in *L. monocytogenes*, especially highlighting the role of the PrfA and σ^B systems, but also TCS (here represented by LisRK) and sRNAs (in blue). Gene products regulated by both PrfA and σ^B are shown in red. Dotted lines indicate regulatory interactions not yet fully elucidated. Please see text for further details.

(response regulator) comprise the two-component signal transduction system. Once outside, the AIP is recognized by the HK AgrC, which in turn activates the RR AgrA. RNAIII, an sRNA expressed divergently from the *agr*-locus, seems to function as a crucial effector molecule and control the expression of several virulence factors in *S. aureus* [156]. Analysis of the genome sequence of *L. monocytogenes* revealed the presence of a QS/TCS system with high similarity to the Agr system of *S. aureus*, but a regulatory RNAIII has not been identified [152, 157]. The Agr system has been shown to be involved in adhesion and the early steps of biofilm formation [158–160]. However, experimental data on the role of the *L. monocytogenes* Agr system in virulence are somewhat contradictory [152, 161].

Another TCS implicated in *L. monocytogenes* virulence is the LisRK system. This plays a role in stress-sensing and in modulating the virulence potential of *L. monocytogenes* [153]. A Δ *lisK* mutant strain (LisK is the membrane-bound sensory kinase, HK) displays a growth phase-dependent response to acidic conditions [153]. In addition it seems to be involved in the ability of the pathogen to tolerate important antimicrobial agents used in food and medicine, such as nisin and the cephalosporin family of antibiotics [162]. Furthermore, LisRK appears to play a role in *Listeria* virulence, with the Δ *lisK* mutant strain being approximately 10-fold less virulent than the parent wild-type strain [153]. This TCS also plays a role in regulating the osmotolerance of this bacterium, given that a mutation in *lisK* resulted in a significant reduction in

the ability of *L. monocytogenes* to tolerate environments with elevated osmolarity [40]. Furthermore, LisRK has been shown to play an important role in the expression of HtrA (a putative serine protease, homologous to HtrA from *Escherichia coli* and identified as a stress response protein, essential for the pathogenicity of several Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria) and LhrC sRNA (see above), both suggested to be involved in *L. monocytogenes* virulence and pathogenicity [40, 146, 147, 163].

In *L. monocytogenes* the CheY/CheA TCS is associated with the regulation of flagellin expression. Flagellin is encoded by the *flaA* gene and immediately downstream of the *flaA* gene are two genes, *cheY* and *cheA*, encoding peptides that are closely related to the chemotaxis proteins CheY and CheA of *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* [164]. This TCS has also been suggested to play a role in the virulence of *Listeria*, as these proteins seem to be important for both adhesion and invasion of Caco-2 cells [154].

The VirRS system has been identified to contribute to *L. monocytogenes* virulence by regulating the modification of cell surface components. Deletion of *virR* resulted in a severe decrease in virulence, both in mice as well as in invasion cell-culture experiments. While VirR regulates genes that are important for *L. monocytogenes* virulence, it is known that VirR (RR) can be activated independently of VirS (HK), possibly through variations in the level of intracellular acetyl phosphate, as the deletion of *virS* showed no effect

on virulence of the bacterium [155]. A *virR* deletion mutant showed increased sensitivity to antimicrobials used in the food industry and greater loss of membrane integrity when exposed, for example, to nisin [165]. It has been shown that the VirAB ABC transporter is required for VirR regulation of *L. monocytogenes* virulence and resistance to nisin [166]. This putative ABC transporter, designated VirAB, is necessary for VirR function. A $\Delta virAB$ mutant exhibited reduced transcription of VirR-regulated genes and *in vivo* virulence that was similar to that of a $\Delta virR$ deletion mutant [166].

DegU, the orphan RR, is an interesting case as it lacks its corresponding HK. DegU is a transcriptional activator of the *flaA* gene and it contributes to the temperature-dependent regulation of motility and chemotaxis genes [161, 167]. It controls the expression of GmaR, a protein that functions as an antagonist of MogR (a known flagellar repressor) [168–171]. DegU binds upstream of the *motB* operon, which encodes GmaR. DegU has also been shown to play a role in virulence of *L. monocytogenes*, given that a $\Delta degU$ mutant shows attenuated virulence in mice when compared with the wild-type strain [172]. However, DegU seems to have no influence on the transcription of *prfA*, which suggests another mechanism by which DegU regulates virulence. This suggests that DegU is a pleiotropic regulator of both motility at low temperature and *in vivo* virulence in mice [173]. Because it has no cognate HK, it is speculated that the phosphorylation of DegU is influenced by the intracellular acetyl phosphate pool, providing a link between its phosphorylation state and the metabolic status of the bacteria [172].

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The complex and challenging environments encountered by the versatile pathogen *L. monocytogenes* require highly sensitive and robust regulatory mechanisms to fine tune the expression of the protective mechanisms and virulence factors that collectively influence its fitness (Fig. 4). These are exemplified by the σ^B and PrfA systems, which together help the pathogen to successfully switch from its saprophytic life to being an intracellular pathogen. The complexity of the regulatory checkpoints associated with these regulators underlines the importance of carefully balancing their relative activities to ensure fitness during the transition from food to human host. Understanding these regulatory mechanisms may well be the key that helps find the Achilles heel in this pathogen and ultimately lead to the development of the next generation of antimicrobials.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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